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ENERGY PROBLEMS IN UZBEKISTAN. THEIR SOLUTIONS AND REMEDIAL MEASURES

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, our country has undergone radical changes aimed at developing the economy and improving the living standards of the population. Free economic zones, technoparks and clusters are being established in various regions of the country. At the same time, more attention is paid to the protection of the environment and environmental sustainability than ever before. Such rapid growth in all spheres of society and state life, first of all, leads to an increase in the demand for electricity.

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Introduction. Demand for electricity is growing rapidly. In 2000, one household user used 114 kWh of electricity per month, but by 2018, the figure had increased by 57% to 200 kWh. At the same time, this year the share of the population in the total electricity consumption in the country has reached 26.5%. However, in 1990 this figure was 13.9 percent. Do you see the difference? Moreover, according to forecasts, by 2022 the demand for electricity in the country will increase by 1.7% compared to 2018, including the demand of the population by 1.5 times.

Electricity generation plays an important role in the Uzbek economy. It is the most widely used natural gas for its production, accounting for about 87%. In particular, the distribution of natural

resources in our country is as follows: Why the need for a comprehensive approach to this issue? To be honest, it's been a long time coming. Because we go deeper into the subject through numbers and facts, through painful scenes.

90% of electricity in the country is generated by thermal power plants (TPPs). However, the bulk of existing thermal power plants, or 84 percent, were commissioned 50 years ago. Relatively old such devices, of course, do not meet the requirements of the times at all. Because they are so obsolete, they reduce electricity production, create shortages, and consume large amounts of fuel. As a result, the cost of electricity generated is rising. The average consumer is almost unaware of this.

At present, the length of power grids in the country is 254.8 thousand kilometers. Of these, 218.4 thousand kilometers are low-voltage distribution networks with a voltage of 0.4-10 kV. 62.4% of them have a service life of more than 30 years. The obsolescence of the distribution network has led to significant power losses. That's 20 percent of the total electricity generated by thermal power plants. Imagine that one-fifth of the light and heat we produce is blown into the air. What can be done to address these shortcomings, eliminate the shortcomings and prevent waste?

In addition, 86% of the electricity generated by thermal power plants in the country. The distribution of shares is as follows: Modernization of power equipment of thermal power plants (40%), modernization of electrical systems for transmission and distribution of electricity (57%), transformer substations (52%) and substations (21%);

- Launch of new generator capacity (which will increase electricity production by 20-40%);
- Periodic scheduled repairs to keep existing power equipment in working order.

It is clear that these good and important deeds will not be done easily. That means a lot of money, a lot of willpower, a lot of hard work and a lot of support from the people. Therefore, in addition to Uzbekenergo's own funds, international financial institutions and the Uzbek Development and Reconstruction Fund have agreed to modernize the country's energy systems and install new, cost-effective ones instead of high-cost devices. It is planned that the funds of the army will also be directed.

Another issue that needs to be addressed is water and air. The main part of the cost of electricity generation is the cost of fuel and energy resources (natural gas, fuel oil, coal). Given that the figure is

currently 43% and their prices are rising on the world market, how reasonable is it to maintain the current tariffs for electricity?

This is because the cost of resources, combined with the cost of use and the arrears of payments, creates a painful picture of the problem. Such problems can adversely affect the reliability and quality of the power supply.

There are 42 power units in the country, almost 50% of which are spiritually and physically obsolete.

From the words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "We are producing electricity by burning currency", it is clear that from now on there is a high probability of its economical use and the Uzbek government's policy of abandoning gas turbines. possible.

It should be noted that this work can be applied in the field of natural resources - gas and oil (Shurtangaz, Gazli, Mubarek, etc.). It is possible that there are these problems in this area as well.

The fact is that Uzbekenergo has received 1,398.2 billion soums from its own funds to implement investment projects for the modernization of obsolete equipment, as well as to repay loans. I need Rs. As a result, by the end of 2020, the deficit of

Trouble shooting Suggestions.

1. Existing obsolete steam turbines can be replaced by high-temperature integrated parabolocylindrical solar collectors. Their heating temperature is 200-600 degrees:
2. Low temperature solar absorbers can be used in thermal power plants and district heating boilers. If the water temperature of 10 degrees is raised to 40 degrees by these absorbers, the fuel can be used to obtain the remaining high temperature. The price is much cheaper:
3. A memorandum on the development of solar energy in Uzbekistan will be signed between Germany and Uzbekistan. Under the memorandum, the German government is ready to provide financial assistance and cooperation for the development of solar energy in Uzbekistan. This can be seen in the projects of the German Aerospace and Energy Center in Africa and the Arab world.
4. Establishment of a joint technical university in Uzbekistan. To involve and employ our compatriots studying and working abroad.
5. Production of solar heat collectors on the basis of local raw materials based on German experience and technology. At the initial stage, the work will be carried out in collaboration with German experts. This work will then be carried out directly by local industry professionals.
6. With the help of various solar collectors and measuring instruments, appropriate advocacy

work will be intensified to conduct on-site research and increase the population's interest in installing solar energy in their homes. Various research institutes and manufacturing enterprises, as well as kindergartens, will be the main basis for this work.

8. For various reasons - to make effective use of our compatriots coming to Uzbekistan on business trips or during work and study holidays, to organize various meetings, open dialogues and conversations with them in the field, to invite them to press clubs, to convey their knowledge and experience to students studying in the field.

9. At least once a month, it is necessary to organize TV and radio projects on the effective use of alternative energy in various sectors of our economy through the central television and radio channels of Uzbekistan. Ensuring the regularity of such advocacy work and conducting advocacy work in close cooperation with representatives of the industry.

10. It is necessary to create an alternative energy portal on the Internet, in which the analysis of collaborative work with local scientists and foreign experts will be widely covered.

11. Organize targeted training for Uzbek youth in the field of energy, including solar, wind biogas, geothermal, at doctoral, master's and bachelor's degrees in German universities.

12. It is necessary to establish a department under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the improvement and development of the energy sector or an Advisory Council consisting of leading scientists and specialists. The main tasks of this department or the Council will be to attract investment in the energy sector, as well as to develop education and science, and to cooperate directly with foreign experts. It would be useful to develop a separate program to design and implement the above practical proposals.

How can we change the way people think about it?

What can be done to ensure that consumers use electricity sparingly, economically and wisely? Is there a way? If you find the rest, the snow will burn. Kars is out of control. The only rational solution to this problem is for the state and the general public to jointly reconsider the system of tariffs, to set strict social norms for the use of electricity, taking into account foreign experience.

Conclusion. Problems with energy resources and their use are being addressed on a regular basis. Rational use of energy resources is a global issue not only in Uzbekistan, but also on the planet. The goal can be achieved by taking the following steps.

- Reducing the state's share in the energy sector, creating favorable conditions for attracting private investment and preventing unreasonable increases in the cost of electricity supply to final consumers through the best proposals and the latest technologies;

- Organize the formation of a competitive energy market, develop and approve market rules that ensure equal rights and transparency for all participants, and establish regular monitoring of compliance with these rules by all market participants;

- Introduction of norms on social protection of low-income and vulnerable segments of the population in the formation of electricity tariffs;

- Introduction of a mechanism to stimulate power plants, the main equipment of which consists of the technology of local manufacturers;

- Liberalization of natural and liquefied gas trade and improvement of service quality in accordance with international business practice;

- Establishment of economically justified separate tariffs for liquefied gas transportation and distribution services within the country.

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